

AN ANALYSIS OF PANCASILA VALUES ON COMPANY PRODUCTIVITY PERFORMANCE IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

This study used a survey research design. This research is included in quantitative research to determine the behavior of individuals or groups in the application of a Pancasila value-based business strategy. Basically, the research design is descriptive because a survey questionnaire has been designed and formulated. This study is also a case study, conducting in Jakarta and surrounding areas as representation of Indonesia as a whole. A case study has been described as an intensive, systematic investigation of a single individual, group, community or some other unit in which the researcher examines in-depth data relating to several variables. This research shows that there are 116 people (21.1%) who stated Strongly Agree on business performance in the production sector. This number mostly came from trading companies with 44 people (8.0%), but relatively speaking these four types of companies have advantages in the field of production performance. This is indicated by the proportion of respondents who work in the four companies are relatively the same. The results of the production performance of the four types of companies studied were also shown by the Pearson Chi-Square test of 0.265; which means that there is no real difference at the 10 percent significance level. This shows that the implementation of Pancasila strategic management in the production sector in manufacturing, trading, education and other service companies has a uniform performance from one another. Meanwhile, with the application of Pancasila strategic management, 26.0% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement Companies have become more efficient in managing their business. Meanwhile 27.2% of respondents stated strongly agree with the statement Companies experience fewer complaints in the quality of their products and services. This proves that the implementation of Pancasila-based strategic management in the field of production performance is still low and needs to be improved.

Keywords: Analysis; Pancasila Values; Company Productivity; Performance; Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

Complementary social planting results can increase the productivity of micro businesses. This is in accordance with the world view of the unity of divine law which is termed in the Koran as oneness of God or its equivalent to divine law and also the unity of knowledge, described in the form of a general socio-economic paradigm. This world view is then used to discuss the complementary relationship between microenterprise and the embedded social environment, which consists of community and business. The reciprocal relationship of participatory development which is explained by means of a circular cause and effect between the variables representing the community, business and micro-enterprises is a specific example of the application of the Islamic episteme about the unity of science in existing entities. In embedded learning systems. Such a learning system is governed by the episteme of the unity of knowledge as described in the Qur'an and Sunnah. These together form the basis of every methodological inquiry and application of Islam.

Moral legitimacy, legitimacy related to input and discursiveness affect productivity. Humanism can prepare managers for the unique conditions and demands that characterize the personnel

and meeting services sector. If strategic management of Pancasila could be practiced extensively, these life lessons would undoubtedly improve the overall quality of life by reducing interpersonal conflict and bullying; prevent accidental injury and death; and increasing work productivity, environmental sustainability, and life satisfaction. Techniques for operationalizing these humanistic guidelines are presented, which demonstrate the social validity of integrating certain principles of humanism with behaviorism. The result of the synthesis is the existence of humanistic behaviorism in the application of several humanistic fundamentals so that behaviorism is more acceptable, effective, and sustainable on a large scale.

The structure of the production regime, the accessibility of domestic institutions, and the ideology of the labor center. This synthesis is derived from the influence of the nationalism strategy on productivity in maintaining complicated relations with the state. The labor response to international economic integration and industrial restructuring in the apparel and automotive industries establishes that the practice of multinational companies to outsource and segment production processes within and across countries has put pressure on wages and trade unions. Weakened. This synthesis argues that the response of the labor force to this trend is shaped by the structure of the production regime, the accessibility of domestic institutions, and the ideology of labor centers.

Stakeholders, environment and society have an effect on productivity. This synthesis is based on an innovation-oriented business model for sustainability. It expands the original business model canvas by adding an environmental layer based on a life cycle perspective and a social layer based on a stakeholder perspective (Joyce & Paquin, 2016). Taken together, the application of the democratizing variables to the business model makes more explicit how organizations generate different types of values economic, environmental and social. Visually representing the business model through this canvas tool supports the development and communication of a more holistic and integrated business model display; which also supports creative innovation towards more sustainable business models.

REVIEW OF PAST LITERATURE

Impact of Divine Variable on Productivity

The vision of divinity, including the balance of nature in improving company performance, has begun to be developed. This is with one another as a result of the outbreak of the corona pandemic which has changed the balance of nature at work (Caesar & Fei, 2018) Initially considered a problem that must be managed by individual employees, work-life balance has now taken a central position in practice and policy employment (Kim, 2014).

The recent increase in attention from organizations to work-life balance issues is directly related to the many benefits that have been found to be associated with work-life balance for both employers and employees (Emslie & Hunt, 2009; Jones, Burke & Westman, 2013).

On the employee side, an increase in work-life balance has a positive impact on their psychological well-being whereas organizations are able to increase affective organizational

commitment, job satisfaction, worker involvement, organizational citizenship behavior and employee productivity through appropriate work-life balance practices and policies. (Cegarra-Leiva, Sánchez-Vidal & Gabriel Cegarra-Navarro, 2012; Emslie & Hunt, 2009; Jones et al., 2013).

The problem of reduced work-life balance is present in all sectors of work but is more common in certain industries because of the nature of the work (Hill, Miller, Weiner & Colihan, 1998; Lingard & Francis, 2004; Tausig & Fenwick, 2001). For example, industries such as hospitality and shipping have a high incidence of reducing work-life balance due to the complex and demanding nature of the conditions in which people work in these sectors (Chiang, Birtch & Kwan, 2010; Thomas, Sampson & Zhao, 2003).

Natural balance as a dimension of divine vision can have a positive effect on company productivity. In particular, for the shipping industry, seafarers working on cruise ships and bulkers are likely to complain of stressful working conditions that negatively impact their long-term work-life balance (Barnett et al., 2017). This has an impact on the need for a balance of work and free time to improve performance.

The world view of the unity of divine law which is termed in the Koran as Tauhid (the unity of God or its equivalent of divine law and also the unity of knowledge) is described in the form of a general socio-economic paradigm (Alam Choudhury & Harahap, 2009). This world view is then used to discuss the complementary relationship between micro-enterprises and the embedded social environment, which consists of community and business.

Value of Humanitarian on Productivity

Ignoring personal, family and social aspects and increasing emphasis on the financial bottom line has created inequality in the lives of workers at all levels. The result is stress in life, conflicts in the family, social distortions, decreased performance and low productivity. (Anwar et al., 2013) To overcome this, a work-life balance is needed which is not a recommendation but a divine command. This research was conducted to seek answers to a simple question: what must organizations do to create balance?

The results show that training and development, professional commitment and adherence to core values, time management, clarity of vision, goals and objectives, employee-human relations, salary packages and a conducive work environment and innovation are areas to focus on. Organization and acting on the basis of making WLB. These findings appear to be generalized but the rankings and priorities are unique and therefore may be of interest to many organizations.

Since the early 1980s, service management representatives have sought to differentiate service from the manufacturing industry and highlight the special features that characterize the service industry. However, others claim that such a distinction is unnecessary, and that services will benefit from technocratic thinking and clear standardization to improve quality, productivity and profitability. (Sandoff, 2012)

The service business is very personnel-intensive and many meetings take place between managers, employees and customers. Using standards is not sufficient for this endeavor and managers are important as role models. Conversely, it is said that managers need 'proper' education to be able to fulfill what does not follow patterns of reasoning and rational action. Humanism was introduced as an important aspect of future management education.

Humanism can prepare managers for the unique conditions and demands that characterize the personnel and meeting services sector. (Geller, 2015) Seven evidence-based guidelines for improving quality and increasing the frequency of desired behavior are described and illustrated as relevant to benefit human well-being and well-being. If practiced extensively, these life lessons are sure to improve the overall quality of life by reducing interpersonal conflict and bullying; prevent accidental injury and death; and increase work productivity, environmental sustainability, and life satisfaction.

The first three guidelines reflect applied behavioral science principles of positive reinforcement, observational learning, and behavior-based feedback. The next four life lessons stem primarily from humanism. Techniques for operationalizing these humanistic guidelines are presented, demonstrating the social validity of integrating certain principles of humanism with behaviorism. The result is the existence of humanistic behaviorism in the application of several humanistic fundamentals to make behaviorism more acceptable, effective, and sustainable on a large scale.

There is currently a major transformation with increasing urbanization, climate change, loss of biodiversity, increasing disparities, etc. (Girard, 2016) a new development model is needed, one that can better meet everyone's needs. The revised traditional city model, associated with specific areas, with localism, to recognize local identities that make a difference with their specific inheritance, based on circular/ closed processes and strong relationships between cities and regions; on the face

Face-to-face and not just for digital/ virtual relationships that pay attention to the valorization of local tangible and intangible resources, exploiting differences to make the site more attractive for localization of talent, investment, special skills, i.e. to increase productivity, assuming the centrality of the concrete relationship between cities and regions, between inhabitants and nature. This perspective of moving towards a new urban paradigm has been applied in several small cities.

Nationalism Value on Productivity

Mazumdar's (2012) research shows why economic nationalism in India contributed to and coincided with the liberalization process that began in 1991, the year of substantial reform. This research captures the faces of Indian capitalists from seeking refuge to embracing globalization by examining the views of the capitalist class represented by Indian big business.

This chapter argues that this transformation reflects the evolution of Indian capitalism due to industrialization under the older autonomous strategy. Furthermore, embracing liberalization is possible and necessary for Indian capitalists with the Indian state also adapting to the

necessities of national capitalist development. The state continues to assist the capitalist class in different ways and in turn Indian capital has gained greater influence with the state and greater visibility in the world economy. As a result, Indian capital has grown globally and has become less industrialized and more integrated into global production and financial systems.

The influence of the strategy of nationalism on productivity was developed by Nicoli (2011) during the early years of entrepreneurs in the Italian film industry maintaining a complicated relationship with the state. Arrangements between the joint-stock company and the Italian government in the interwar period are typical.

Initially, Italian banks funded the production, despite difficulties in assessing the potential profitability of a film. Following the rise of Benito Mussolini, the state invested in this industry, viewing it as a means of building nationalism and shaping the country's culture. While the deal hurt the quality of the film, it allowed filmmakers to gain technical experience and acquire production facilities that they could better use later.

The labor response to international economic integration and industrial restructuring in the Latin American apparel and auto industry (Anner, 2002) stipulates that the practice of multinational companies to outsource and segment production processes within and across countries has put downward pressure on wages and trade unions. Weakened. Researchers argue that the response of the labor force to this trend is shaped by the structure of the production regime, the accessibility of domestic institutions, and the ideology of labor centers.

One employment response combines local organizing with transnational advocacy and networks that put pressure on MNCs in their home countries. Other responses do not involve transnationalism, but rather involve deep inner-state relationships between trade unions and the government and / or the business sector in relationships that may involve protection of business from trade unions.

Modern society is challenged by a loss of efficiency in the values of the national system of government and lifestyle. The discourse of corporate social responsibility is built on a conception of organizational legitimacy that does not reflect this change properly (Palazzo & Scherer, 2006).

The circular economy framework has attracted the attention of industry and academia and has received strong policy support (Inigo & Blok, 2019). It is currently considered a potent solution to sustainability, despite constant criticism of its oversimplification and lack of consideration of socio-ethical issues. Correspondingly, the concept of RRI has emerged strongly with a strong focus on integrating social will into innovation under the principles of transparency, democracy and shared responsiveness.

In this paper, researchers critically examine the literature on circular economy to find out how the different focus of RRI can provide an innovation governance framework to strengthen a circular economy framework (Inigo & Blok, 2019). There are two main ways in which RRI can advance a circular economy: first, anticipating unanticipated consequences, helping to break disciplinary boundaries and recognizing systemic boundaries that are not currently

considered; and second, integration of socio-ethical issues in PK, and overcoming the social implications of PK through stakeholder participation. However, future research must look at the remaining blind spots of circular economy, such as non-technological innovation, demand-side innovation, and business model development. With that in mind, researchers suggest a research agenda for the joint development of such a framework.

Environmental innovation, environmental efficiency, and corporate social responsibility practices define a large part of the industry's current sustainability agenda (Bocken et al., 2014). While important, they alone are not sufficient to deliver the holistic changes necessary to achieve long-term social and environmental sustainability. We can drive corporate innovations that significantly change the way companies operate to ensure better sustainability.

Democratic Values on Productivity

A sustainable business model combines a triple bottom line approach and considers the interests of various stakeholders, including the environment and society. They are important in driving and implementing corporate innovation for sustainability, can help embed sustainability into business goals and processes, and serve as a key driver of competitive advantage. Many innovative approaches can contribute to realizing sustainability through business models, but they have not been structured under the unifying theme of business model innovation.

A review of the literature and business practices has identified a wide variety of examples of mechanisms and solutions that can contribute to business model innovation for sustainability. The samples are collected and analyzed to identify defining patterns and attributes that can facilitate categorization. The archetype of a sustainable business model is introduced to explain the grouping of mechanisms and solutions that can contribute to building a business model for sustainability.

The aim of this archetype is to develop a common language with which to accelerate the development of sustainable business models in research and practice. The basic pattern is: Maximizing material and energy efficiency; Create value from 'waste'; Replace it with renewable energy and natural processes; Provides functionality rather than ownership; Adopting a stewardship role; Encourage sufficiency; Redirecting business for society / environment; and Develop scale-up solutions.

The Three Layers Business Model Canvas is a tool for exploring innovation-oriented business models for sustainability. It expands the original business model canvas by adding two layers: an environmental layer based on a life cycle perspective and a social layer based on a stakeholder perspective (Joyce & Paquin, 2016). Taken together, the three layers of the business model make more explicit how organizations generate different types of value - economic, environmental and social. Visually representing the business model through this canvas tool supports the development and communication of a more holistic and integrated business model display; which also supports creative innovation towards more sustainable business models.

This paper presents a three-tier business model canvas tool and describes its key features through a re-analysis of the Nestlé business model. This new tool contributes to sustainable business model research by providing design tools that structure the issues of sustainability in business model innovation. Also, it creates two new dynamics for analysis: horizontal coherence and vertical coherence.

Social Justice Variable on Productivity

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) can help overcome poverty, social exclusion and other development challenges (Newell & Frynas, 2007). Balance of responsibilities between states, markets and civil society in addressing these issues and meeting the United Nations Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). What new tools, strategies and methodologies are needed to capitalize on the positive potential contribution of business to development and prevent irresponsible companies? This special issue brings together a dynamic mix of academics and development specialists to tackle these themes in a focused and innovative way.

In this article, the researcher considers some of the cross-cutting themes and insights raised by contributions. The aim of this introduction and special issue is to begin to fill in gaps in our understanding of how, when and in what ways business can help reduce poverty, while realizing the equally strong potential of the business community to exacerbate poverty. Taking specific CSR, to get a more complete picture of how businesses engage in the development process.

With the radical changes in information production introduced by the Internet, we stand at an important transitional moment, says Yochai Benkler in this thought-provoking book (Benkler, 2006). The phenomenon he describes as social production is reshaping markets, while at the same time offering new opportunities for increasing individual freedom, cultural diversity, political discourse and justice. But this result is simply unavoidable: a systematic campaign to protect the industrialized information economy entrenched in the past century threatens the promise of today's burgeoning network information environment.

In the comprehensive social theory of the Internet and the networked information economy, Benkler explains how patterns of information, knowledge, and cultural production change - and shows that the way information and knowledge is available can limit or enlarge the way people can be creative. And express yourself. He explained the various legal and policy choices we face and stated that there is much to gain - or lose - by the decisions we make today.

The aim of the paper is to advance research on sustainable innovation by adopting a business model perspective (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013). Through a confrontation of the literature on the two topics, researchers found that research on sustainable innovation tends to ignore the ways in which companies need to combine value propositions, upstream and downstream value chain organization, and financial models to achieve sustainability. Innovation to the market.

Therefore, we review the current literature on business models in the context of technological, organizational and social innovation. Since the current literature does not offer a general conceptual definition of a sustainable business model, we propose examples of normative

requirements that business models must meet to support sustainable innovation. Finally, the researcher sketches an outline of the research agenda by formulating a number of guiding questions.

Subsequent papers apply a social exchange perspective to understand the internal contingencies of the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and performance (De Clercq et al., 2010). It focuses on two aspects of social interaction among functional managers (procedural justice and trust), as well as on their organizational commitment, as a potential increase for the successful exploitation of firms' entrepreneurial opportunities. A study of 232 companies based in Canada found several positive moderating effects:

The EO-performance relationship was stronger for higher levels of procedural fairness, trust, and organizational commitment. Moreover, consistent with the systems approach to organizational possibilities, the EO performance relationship is stronger when the social context of the organization approaches the "ideal" configuration of procedural fairness, trust, and organizational commitment that is most conducive to knowledge exchange within the organization. The study implications and future research directions are discussed.

Table 1: Impact of Pancasila Strategic Variables on Productivity

Dimension	Impact on	Result
Divinity	The complementary social planting results can increase the productivity of micro businesses.	Significant
Humanity	Moral legitimacy, input-related legitimacy and discursiveness affect productivity.	Significant
Nationalism	he structure of the production regime, the accessibility of domestic institutions, and the ideology of the labor center	Significant
Democracy	Stakeholders, environment and society have an effect on productivity.	Significant
Social justice	Distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice have positive and negative effects on productivity.	Significant

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a survey research design. This research is included in quantitative research to determine the behavior of individuals or groups in the application of a Pancasila value-based business strategy. Basically, the research design is descriptive because a survey questionnaire has been designed and formulated. This study is also a case study, conducting in Jakarta and surrounding areas as representation of Indonesia as a whole. A case study has been described as an intensive, systematic investigation of a single individual, group, community or some other unit in which the researcher examines in-depth data relating to several variables.

Using case studies in this research means that the holistic nature of nursing care can be addressed. Furthermore, when describing the steps undertaken while using a case study

approach, this method of research allows the researcher to take a complex and broad topic, or phenomenon, and narrow it down into a manageable research question(s). By collecting qualitative or quantitative datasets about the phenomenon, the researcher gains a more in-depth insight into the phenomenon than would be obtained using only one type of data.

Respondents of the Study

As research participants, respondents were selected from four (4) clusters representing the company business sector, namely the manufacturing, trading, education, and service clusters. The determination of the different clusters is intended to determine the differences in the responses of respondents in one company area with responses in various fields in other companies.

Research respondents were conducted in companies around Metropolitan Jakarta, which represent companies in Indonesia. The selection of companies was determined by considering that at the time of the study there were not many choices, because the country was in a pandemic corona disaster so it was difficult to find respondents in other places.

Respondent of the study include manager and employee with proportion of 1: 10 so that in the research this two groups will be taken into consideration. The companies will also be grouped based on its relevancy.

RESULT OF THE STUDY

This research shows that there are 116 people (21.1%) who stated Strongly Agree on business performance in the production sector. This number came from manufacturing companies with 37 people (6.7%), trading 44 people (8.0%), education 17 people (3.1%), and services 18 people (3.3%). Relatively, the four types of companies have advantages in the field of production performance. This is indicated by the proportion of respondents who work in the four companies are relatively the same.

The results of the production performance of the four types of companies studied were also shown by the Pearson Chi-Square test of 0.265; Likelihood Ratio of 0.251; and the Linear-by-Linear Association value of 0.271, all of which stated that there was no significant difference at the 10 percent significance level. This shows that the implementation of Pancasila strategic management in the production sector in manufacturing, trading, education and other service companies has a uniform performance from one another.

Meanwhile, with the application of Pancasila strategic management, 26.0% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement Companies have become more efficient in managing their business. Meanwhile 27.2% of respondents stated strongly agree with the statement Companies experience fewer complaints in the quality of their products and services. This proves that the implementation of Pancasila-based strategic management in the field of production performance is still low and needs to be improved.

		Effective			Total
		Low	High		
Efficient	Low	Count	372	36	408
		% of Total	67.5%	6.5%	74.0%
	High	Count	27	116	143
		% of Total	4.9%	21.1%	26.0%
Total		Count	399	152	551
		% of Total	72.4%	27.6%	100.0%
		Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square		277,046 ^a	1	.000	
Continuity Correction ^b		273,439	1	.000	
Likelihood Ratio		266,992	1	.000	
Fisher's Exact Test					.000
Linear-by-Linear Association		276,543	1	.000	
N of Valid Cases		551			

DISCUSSION

This research is supported by the existence of significant differences in production performance between aspects of effectiveness and efficiency in manufacturing, trading, and education and service companies. There were 372 respondents (67.5%) who stated that the efficiency and effectiveness of the company were still low. Meanwhile, 116 respondents (21.6%) stated that the efficiency and effectiveness of the company was high. Between the two groups, there were 36 respondents (6.5%) who stated that the effectiveness was high, the efficiency was low, and 27 respondents (4.9%) stated that the other respondents said that the effectiveness was low, the efficiency was high. These results indicate that the implementation of Pancasila-based strategic management in the production sector in the companies under study is still not as expected. This is supported by the value of the Pearson Chi-Square test, Continuity Correction b, Likelihood Ratio, Fisher's Exact Test, and the Linear-by-Linear Association, all of which state that there is a significant difference between the observed frequency and the expected frequency at the 1 percent significance level.

Moral legitimacy, legitimacy related to input and discursiveness affect productivity. Humanism can prepare managers for the unique conditions and demands that characterize the personnel and meeting services sector. (Geller, 2015) If strategic management of Pancasila could be practiced extensively, these life lessons would undoubtedly improve the overall quality of life by reducing interpersonal conflict and bullying; prevent accidental injury and death; and increasing work productivity, environmental sustainability, and life satisfaction. Techniques for operationalizing these humanistic guidelines are presented, which demonstrate the social validity of integrating certain principles of humanism with behaviorism. The result of the

synthesis is the existence of humanistic behaviorism in the application of several humanistic fundamentals so that behaviorism is more acceptable, effective, and sustainable on a large scale.

Stakeholders, environment and society have an effect on productivity. This synthesis is based on an innovation-oriented business model for sustainability. It expands the original business model canvas by adding an environmental layer based on a life cycle perspective and a social layer based on a stakeholder perspective (Joyce & Paquin, 2016). Taken together, the application of the democratizing variables to the business model makes more explicit how organizations generate different types of values - economic, environmental and social. Visually representing the business model through this canvas tool supports the development and communication of a more holistic and integrated business model display; which also supports creative innovation towards more sustainable business models.

Distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice have a positive and negative effect on productivity. This synthesis is based on a social exchange perspective to understand the possible internal relationships between entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and performance (De Clercq et al., 2010). It focuses on two aspects of social justice interactions among functional managers (procedural justice and trust), as well as on their organizational commitment, as a potential increase for the successful exploitation of corporate entrepreneurial opportunities.

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